

A novel architecture for the detection, exploitation and historical archival of indoor semantic trajectories: A case study on nursing homes

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Abstract

We introduce an automatic system, based on indoor positioning techniques, aimed at improving the quality of service of a nursing home. It tracks the location of both residents and caregivers and automatically detects the activities taking place. The system presents a hybrid approach for storing large amounts of data, using both a traditional relational database and an ad-hoc compact data structure, enabling compact storage of the information without compromising fast random access. Our proposal is complemented by a graphical user interface that can dynamically display collected trajectories within the facilities. Having access to all this information, our system will be able to evaluate the quality of health care offered to their residents, as well as assess the efficiency of the nursing home as a business.

Keywords: Indoor trajectories; Activity deduction; Compact Data Structures; Healthcare.

1. Introduction

We present a novel hardware and software architecture which has as its main goal the assessment, and possibly the improvement, of the quality of service provided in healthcare facilities. In our case, this healthcare facility is a nursing home for the elderly. Our architecture is based on the combination of several key elements: an Indoor Positioning System (IPS) used to track the movements of caregivers and residents; a storage module that is capable of managing the large volume of data the IPS produces; an automatic activity deduction module that reveals both the types of interactions between people and the standalone activities that are taking place; and a user-friendly user interface to exploit all this information.

Our proposed software solution encompasses two main aspects: data processing and exploitation services. On the one hand, data processing tackles Big Data management, as the amount of tracked positions (each minute by default) of residents and caregivers grows considerably each month. Compact data structures, an interesting approach for dealing with Big Data scenarios,

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were used as a foundation of this system. Compact data structures compress data in a self-indexed way, avoiding decompressing the data to exploit it, that is, the data can be queried in compressed form. This strategy allows the system to achieve a 1.44% compression ratio in the best scenarios; i.e. 500 MB can be reduced to 7.2 MB and almost any operation can be solved in main memory.

Besides, data processing also includes the detection of activities taking place. This is based on the position and other information such as the agenda of a person, activity duration, etc. Tracked trajectory fragments in the system are labelled with a semantic tag obtained through activity decision trees.

Finally, the exploitation module includes a novel web interface that aims at connecting all the processed information with the final user. It is worth highlighting the web view that allows to reproduce the movement of the residents/caregivers through the building, along with how much time they spent in each activity.

An Indoor Positioning System or IPS is a network of wireless devices that periodically retrieve the positions of objects or individuals moving in a designated (indoor) space during a given time frame. We have designed and implemented such an IPS for the nursing home using Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) technologies. The technologies used to collect this positional data already exist. Section 2.1 briefly describes these technologies and the reasons that lead us to choose BLE devices.

The information collected by the IPS must be stored in order to exploit it. As explained before, in our context, the amount of data grows rapidly, generating large datasets of long-term historical data that need storage management and efficient exploitation. In order to solve this, we have implemented a new compression strategy, *indRep*, that guarantees low space footprint, while keeping efficient access to the data (in its compressed form). Section 4 introduces more details about our proposed compact data structure.

Considering the positional data, combined with some other contextual information such as the time or the type of person, we have also implemented an activity deduction module capable of identifying the activity that is taking place.

For example, consider that a resident is located, during the usual lunchtime of the nursing home, in the dining room. That means that the resident is most probably *having lunch*, so this activity would be deducted. However, if a bedridden resident is in his or her room at lunchtime, and a caregiver enters the room and exits more than 15 minutes later, the system would also detect the activity *having lunch*. And, finally, if the person was a caregiver, the deducted activity would be *helping with meals*.

This activity deduction is fundamental to determine the quality of service. For example, we would be able to detect if some residents are neglected (staying alone for too long, having an extremely short time in the shower during personal hygiene times, etc.). In the same way, this information can prove useful for optimizing the schedule of the personnel, minimizing wasted time moving through corridors and therefore improving productive time. By detecting such wasted time, some enhancing actions can be done (like reorganizing the use of some dependencies of the building) to address it. More about activity deduction can be found in Section 5.

All the collected and inferred information are accessible via a user-friendly user interface. It can be used for different purposes, from locating one particular person (for example, to quickly find a resident who is receiving a visit) to showing the movements and activities of any given person in a particular time-lapse (that could serve to show the relatives of a resident what he/she did in a particular day and how well he/she was taken care of). We designed and developed an innovative interface to display spatio-temporal data representing trajectories and activities. The

web application also includes basic management tasks, such as worker schedules management and medication assignments updates, but these functionalities are accessory to the architecture presented in this work. Section 6 contains a wider description of the interfaces with screenshots.

For this work, we collaborated with *Mayores*¹, a nursing home located in Spain. The feedback they provided us with was essential to help us understand the full scope of the problems we address with our application. Furthermore, this nursing home serves as a validation scenario for our implementation.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides some background information on IPS technologies and nursing home software. Section 3 presents an overview of our proposed architecture. Sections 4 to 6 describe, respectively, the compression techniques, the activity deduction process and the user interface. Finally, the last Section contains some conclusions and feedback received from the real nursing home where the system was tested.

2. Background

In this Section, we explore different approaches to the problem of indoor positioning tracking, focusing on applications of our technology of choice relevant for the context of this work. Then, we will describe the current software solutions available for assisting in the management of a facility like a nursing home and keeping track of the activities taking place in a normal day of work.

2.1. Indoor positioning technologies

Indoor positioning systems (IPS) are composed by a group of devices used to estimate the micro-locations of moving objects in closed environments, where satellite based positioning systems yield highly inaccurate estimations or fail entirely due to the coverage loss of their signals.

Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) is a modern technology that consumes only up to a tenth of the energy of classic bluetooth solutions. These improvements can be achieved by reducing power-consuming activities such as communication times and data sizes. Thus, BLE is slower, and it is not suitable for transferring large files. However, its energy optimizations enable applications to maximize battery life, which can extend to several years for small devices like bluetooth beacons. The energy optimization is possible because beacons only radiate a low-energy (LE) Bluetooth signal to devices within its radius of action, without any prior synchronization. In essence, this technology allows a number of devices to run pre-established protocols when within the given radius.

These beacons, which in the case of tracking people movements are usually wristbands or other types of wearable devices, are key to IPSs. The LE signal they broadcast every few seconds includes an identifier number. These identifier signals can be detected by other BLE devices, which we will call receivers, located nearby. Receivers can be smart phones (they could identify the nearest beacon) or other, more static, small hardware like Raspberry pi-based computers. In this case, knowing where the receiver is located, we can know the approximate location of the beacon in the facilities.

In a different environment, like for example a museum, beacons (emitters) could be attached in fixed locations and visitors could use an app in their smartphones (receivers) that, detecting

¹<https://mayores.es>

the beacon id, could show some information related to what is being exhibited at that location, or it could track visitors flows and interests (Yoshimura et al., 2017).

The use of bluetooth technology is endorsed by all kind of works in the area of indoor positioning, from consumer behavior among shopping mall visitors (Oosterlinck et al., 2017) to minimizing times in people queues (Alabduljabbar, 2022). There are even previous works exploring the adequacy of bluetooth systems in nursing contexts aiming at proximity detection (Naya et al., 2005). This latter work tried to exploit Bluetooth devices attached to people and certain objects in order to estimate both the room-level proximity of people and objects and the mutual proximity between moving people and objects. The experiments presented in that work showed the viability of Bluetooth-based proximity detection for a nursing context. Even though that work did not really exploit the positioning data as our work intends to do, it is nonetheless an early demonstration of the usefulness of these technologies.

Of course, alternative wireless technologies can be found in the state of the art, being Wireless Fidelity (WiFi) and Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) the most popular among them.

WiFi was invented for computer-to-computer communication so it enables to transfer high amounts of data between two devices quite far apart. However, these and other features (e.g., accuracy, security) result in higher costs and significant energy consumption. As identification and tracking do not require high transfer rates, some works reduced costs implementing hybrid Wi-Fi/Bluetooth solutions, handling the tracking tasks through bluetooth (Baniukeyevic et al., 2013, Zhao et al., 2021).

On the other hand, the RFID (Duroc and Tedjini, 2018) ecosystem has been evolving for several decades now. Its cheap tags made it popular in the logistics and asset-tracking contexts. The main drawback of this technology is the short range it can reach, ideal for scanning assets where the distance between the reader and the tag is minimal (e.g. medicines, packages) but unsuitable for many other situations.

Also, a complex deployment of hardware is required to operate with RFID. In a previous work (Joshi et al., 2014), the authors propose a intricate system for monitoring elderly residents of a nursing home and their belongings (wallet, medicines, etc.) combining RFID technology with various types of sensors (movement, video, etc.). It is important to notice the complexity of this approach (and its resultant cost).

Thus, the technological choice in any tracking system is a well-known cost-distance-accuracy trade-off (Utku et al., 2016). In our work, where the exact position within a room of a person does not matter as long as we are able to locate him/her inside a particular room, there is no need for millimeter accuracy. Also, we do not need to cover great areas, but we do require full room coverage (e.g. some dining rooms may be quite large). Thus, BLE technology was the more reasonable choice.

Several system architectures involving IPS have also been developed. In (Catarinucci et al., 2015), the authors describe an architecture for a smart hospital system (SHS), which uses a combination of technologies: RFID, Wireless sensors, and smartphones. In a sense, our architecture follows a similar approach, with loosely coupled modules that would allow the replacement of any technology, but it has some key differences. Their system includes not only positional information, but also patient physiological parameters (heart rate, for example) and environmental information such as humidity or temperature. Thus, functionalities like emitting an alert when some health problem arises is possible. However, it seems that the only historical data that is stored is physiological or medical, and not the positional information. Since they have only the last known location of a patient, they are not able to perform any analysis of the trajectories travelled by the residents, like our system does (automatic activity detection for both residents

and caregivers). Finally, only residents are monitored on the smart hospital, and not caregivers. Hence, information about possible interactions among them cannot be detected. Specifically regarding data storage, they use a MySQL database and do not give additional information on how they deal with the possibly huge amount of information to be stored. In our case, we use our own compact data structure, *indRep*, to store and query the positional data with much less storage needs.

In (Lau et al., 2023), the authors describe a system aimed at detecting activity behavior deviation in a nursing home using IoT devices (namely, BLE beacons and receivers). They do store historical positional data to perform the analysis but, again, they do not indicate how they store it or deal with a Big Data potential problem.

2.2. Nursing home software

Popular systems among nursing homes combine management software solutions with physical interfaces to ease patient-caregiver communication. The former are Enterprise-Resource-Planning-like information systems that involve several management aspects of the nursing home from an enterprise point of view (human resources, stock management, etc.). The latter are usually a set of distributed buttons that alert nearby caregivers, so they can focus on the necessities of a particular patient (e.g. nurse call buttons in hospitals).

The usual combination in Spain of these technologies is carried out through *Resiplus*^{II} a software solution designed specifically for residence management, and *Helpnex*^{III}, a physical resident-caregiver communication system.

On the one hand, *Resiplus* is a management software for nursing homes and day care centers. It can manage every aspect concerning a nursing home, from employees to providers, with a focus on the resident-related features. It also handles all the administration and billing aspects. The application can also manage employee's schedules, economic data, curriculum, received formation, etc.

On the other hand, *Helpnex* is a calling system that focuses on the interaction between caregivers and residents, as well as controlling the time spent for each service or activity. This includes the ability for the residents to inform of their urgent need for attention, pushing a button beside their beds or in the bathrooms. When a resident activates one of these buttons, notifications are sent, both visual and audible, to inform the caregivers of the existence of this need. Besides, the system also controls the time each caregiver spends with each resident, which could serve as a metric of quality for the provided services. For this purpose, every caregiver has a radio frequency identification (RFID) card which should be used to clock in and clock out every time the caregivers assists a resident. The caregiver can also annotate the type of assistance, choosing among a few fixed possibilities in a tactile panel. Note that this is a manual process prone to human error (for example, a caregiver might forget to clock out the end-time of the interaction with a resident, or choose the incorrect task in the panel).

The installation of *Helpnex* requires a main console, buttons for every bed and bathroom, a tactile screen with a RFID reader attached in each room, an IP console to communicate the different devices with the main console, and special multi-color lights for the visual notifications. *Helpnex* is being used in hospitals, day care centers and nursing homes across more than 20 countries.

^{II}<https://www.addinformatica.com>

^{III}<https://iberhex.es/en/helpnex>

The conjunction of both, Resiplus and Helpnex, offers a complete solution to administer the basic necessities of any nursing home. It can also be used to track the movements of caregivers within the facility (if a caregiver clocks-in in a room, then we can assume he/she is in said room until clocking-out of it). However, the same cannot be said for the movements of the residents, which remain untraceable.

In our particular case, the local nursing home complained about the amounts of time that should be spent by the caregivers feeding the system and the inaccuracies that rush entails. Also, residents movement tracking was a constant concern as it now eases the work of the employees and increases the value of the offered service.

2.3. Ethical and privacy issues

As with any system that collects personal information, our IPS is affected by privacy and ethical issues, given that positional information is considered personal (the authors in (de Montjoye et al., 2013) state that 4 spatio-temporal points randomly chosen are able to identify 95% of the persons). Of course, being in the European Union, the General Data Protection Regulation¹ (GDPR) applies. It states that personal information must be managed in a transparent way, only for its intended use. Only the necessary information must be kept, and it should be in a secure and confidential storage. The interested reader can find more information in (Holcer et al., 2020), where a systematic review of privacy in IPS is offered, or in (Ghubaish et al., 2021), a work that is focused on specific aspects of security during the collection, transmission and storage of (medical) data.

Both the researchers and the nursing home we have used for testing were aware of these implications, and dealt with all the collected data accordingly.

3. System architecture

This Section describes the different elements that compose our system, focusing on collecting, saving, exploiting and visualizing the indoor movement trajectory data in a collaborating nursing home.

As Figure 1 shows, our proposed system has three basic parts: gathering, storage, and exploitation. The gathering module collects information that comes from other systems, such as information about the residents and caregivers coming from other existing management software (e.g. *Resiplus*), and positional data coming from the Indoor Positioning System. The storage module performs some key operations: compressing the positional data, tag the raw trajectories into semantic chunks based on the activity performed in each chunk (e.g. sleeping in the room), and store them. Last, the exploitation module tackles the business logic displaying an interactive user-friendly interface to communicate with our proposed system.

Hence, the IPS collects large volumes of raw data that are processed in the storage module to add semantics while reducing space. The specific information about caregivers and residents (type, schedule, limitations, etc.) enhances the decision tree used to estimate the performed activities in each collected position. At the same time, raw positions are compressed using a state-of-the-art approach, reducing space while enabling data access without full decompression. Then, merging both previous steps, this information is loaded into a compact data structure which will feed the information system along with a relational database for simpler queries. A more detailed look on compression and compact structures is provided in Section 4, while Section 5 discusses how the activity deduction works.

3.1. Data Sources

The gathering module interacts with the IPS and any external third party systems to collect information and integrate it into our system through the storage module. That includes mainly two types of data:

- Positional data gathered through the IPS. There are two main elements involved in collecting this information: the hardware itself, and the software (a sort of middleware) used to communicate with it.
- Data about residents and caregivers. This information is usually handled in nursing homes by specific management software such as *Resiplus* (see Section 2.2 for more details). It includes diverse personal and specific information for residents (e.g. medical condition, emergency contacts, medication, etc.) and workers (e.g. shifts hours, category, schedules, etc.). Our proposed system saves this information in a standard relational database management system (namely, PostgreSQL).

We have implemented an integration software that imports into our system the information managed by *Resiplus*. This information can be further edited using our ad-hoc web application. The integration software is prepared to import data from other third party software, in case the nursing home replaces or complements *Resiplus* with other applications.

Figure 1: Software architecture, our proposal includes three different modules: gathering, storage and exploitation. Source: own work.

3.2. Hardware installation of the Indoor Positioning System

Two of the main operational goals of this work are locating people in a building and registering proximity between them. As mentioned in Section 2.1, there are several hardware options to achieve these objectives, but we have opted to use Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) technology instead of RFID or any other alternative. BLE has been proved to be a low-cost energy efficient

and suitable solution for the specific problematic of a nursing home. Besides, this solution is simpler to deploy than other alternatives.

The only needed hardware elements are BLE beacons and receivers. In our configuration, beacons are small wearable devices that contain a (usually replaceable) battery that can last several years. As for the receivers, we have two types. The first one consists of static elements located in all the rooms in the nursing home, plugged in the power network, and also connected to the WiFi network. We used Raspberry Pi Zero W devices, which are BLE-enabled, to detect the beacons. This detection is made by periodic poll of BLE devices in the radio of the receiver. The frequency of this poll was set initially to be 1 by minute, but we are planning to eventually use a variable frequency based on the time and on the previous activity of the residents. As an example, it is probable that during night hours a lower frequency would suffice because most residents should be asleep in their rooms and the movements of the caregivers with a night shift would adhere to their schedule. The second type of receivers are smartphones. They do not provide any type of location, neither exact nor approximate, but they are able to find the nearest beacon to them.

Regarding the distribution of the hardware used, it is as follows:

1. There is a receiver (specifically, a Raspberry Pi Zero W) in every room. Some larger areas such as common areas and dining rooms can have more than one. There are also several receivers along the corridors.
2. Each resident has a beacon. They should wear it at all times.
3. Each caregiver has both a beacon and a receiver (a smartphone). They should carry both during their working hours.

Figure 2: Hardware architecture example displaying the actual placement of beacons and receivers. Source: own work.

Figure 2 shows a schematic example of a small building, consisting of two rooms with the positioning hardware installed. With this design, we are able to determine in which room each person is at any time instant. By tracking these positions along a sufficiently long interval of time, it is possible to gather their trajectories. Since every beacon is assigned to a person, and we know if he or she is a resident or a caregiver, that will help to identify the different interactions between caregivers and residents.

The smartphones provided to the caregiver, which use a specifically made application, also take advantage of the positioning system. The app is able to detect the nearest resident and facilitates the caregiver all the personal and medical information they might need, without having

to perform any search. The app can also record and send the interactions between the caregiver and the resident to the main system.

A note on technology versions: the beacons currently use BLE with Bluetooth 4.x, which is based on signal strength (the location of a beacon is assigned to the location of the receiver that reports it with higher strength). It could be argued that the reported indoor positions would not be sufficiently accurate, but in our case we only need to know in which room the person was or who they interacted with. A theoretical future upgrade to Bluetooth 5.1, which bases its location protocols on angles (Angle of Departure and Angle of Arrival of the signal) would improve the accuracy of the location substantially. In any case, the hardware is dealt with by a third party software that communicates with the gathering module via a REST API. This would allow us to switch technologies (to Bluetooth 5.1 or any other positioning system) with almost no changes in our system.

4. Compression Strategy

As one of the main goals of our system is to efficiently store and query all the daily routines of the inhabitants of a nursing home, the collected data will increase quickly. Compact data structures (Navarro, 2016) are a family of general-purpose data structures that combine compressed data representation with efficient query support. They have self-indexing properties that allow them to store data with minimal space consumption while enabling their processing without decompression (or, at most, a minimal decompression). In addition, the compressed data is more likely to fit into main memory, which speeds up queries due to the reduction in disk accesses (Plattner and Zeier, 2012).

Compact data structures have strengthened all kind of solutions, from bioinformatics (Rossi et al., 2022) to document data mining (Fujishige et al., 2019). In particular, some recent works apply these techniques to deal with trajectory-based problems in both free trajectories (Brisaboa et al., 2019) and network-constrained trajectories (Brisaboa et al., 2022).

Luckily, in our context, there are only a very limited amount of places people inside the facilities can visit, so a great ratio of repetitiveness is expected. For example, the sequence *having breakfast in the dining room* after *taking a shower in the personal room* and *walk* may be performed several consecutive days by the same resident, and even by several residents.

We can exploit this redundancy in order to save space. As the positioning data is essentially a sequence of location identifiers, in an enclosed space, connected by a finite number of corridors we can use the same techniques used in text compression.

A well-known algorithm in this field is *RePair* (Larsson and Moffat, 2000). This lossless grammar-based algorithm traverses several times the entire sequence saving in a dictionary a rule for each repeated pair of identifiers. As an example, if we consider the sequence *ABCAB*, *RePair* will create a rule $X \rightarrow AB$; resulting in the compressed sequence *XCX*.

We decided that *RePair* would be a great basis for our compression. Nonetheless, in order to exploit the data compressed by *RePair* it is always necessary to start decompressing the sequence from the beginning. This is why we designed *indRep*, an enhanced solution based on *RePair* that uses additional data structures for allowing fast random access to the compressed sequence. Thus, a vector containing all positions registered is compressed using *RePair* and tagged with information about dates, residents, etc.

Figure 3 displays a simplified example on how this compact vector is generated. A sequence of simple positions recorded each 5 minutes is compressed using *RePair*. Therefore, new rules

Figure 3: Data compression example. The RePair algorithm is enriched with auxiliary structures that allow faster queries. Source: own work.

are created for repetitive subsequences in order to reduce the length of the original sequence. These rules may be composed by other rules, as it is the case for rule X, depicted in the figure. The power of this method is reflected in the saved sequence for person P_3 , where 5 consecutive positions in the dining room (equivalent to 25 minutes in that place) are stored using a single character (X). As stated before, during the compression process, additional information is stored to enhance the exploitation and facilitate the activity deduction. Thus, the example let us rapidly travel to the positions of the resident P_1 on the 12th of July 2022. If he/she walked out of his/her room at first time in the morning, walked the aisle, and stayed in the dining room for 20 minutes it is reasonable to infer that this resident was having breakfast.

We validated both the space efficiency and the query performance of *indRep* using simulated data based on the real distribution of beacons and schedules of the collaborating nursing home. Our experiments showed that our proposal was able to achieve a very competitive compression ratio while allowing access to the positioning information of any user, in any given day and time of day, in a matter of microseconds.

To illustrate the compression and query capabilities of *indRep*, consider for example the sequence of positioning data of 60 users (whether they are caregivers or residents is irrelevant) during a time frame of 1 year. Assuming we store the positioning information of every user every minute, and that we only store the integer value identifying the detected location, it would take roughly 126 MB (1,440 minutes in a day * 365 days * 60 users * 4 bytes in an integer) of disk space if we store the data in a traditional database. *indRep* is able to compress this with a reduction of the space footprint by at least 91%. meaning we could store all the trajectories of the users in just 12 MB.

Let us compare this metric with the results that could be achieved by simply compressing the data in a ZIP format (a standard lossless compression format used across many programs, both commercial and open-source). Our experiments showed that ZIP compression could reduce the space footprint of the data by at least 94%, meaning 128 MB becomes around 8 MB. While this is even smaller than the result we achieve using *indRep*, it is impossible to directly access any arbitrary segment of the data in a ZIP compressed file without the prior decompression of the totality of the data, whereas, with our data structure, we can query the compressed data without decompressing it.

Additionally, it should be noted that these metrics are assuming a worst-case scenario for our data structures, where we assume a relatively low level of repetition within the positioning data. Our experiments demonstrate that in a scenario with a higher level of repetition in the data, *indRep* can reduce the space requirement of storing the data in a traditional database by upward of 99%, with the ZIP compression topping its performance at around the 98% mark.

A detailed explanation of *indRep* internal structures and behavior, as well as the experimental evaluation of the data structure, can be found in previous works (Fariña et al., 2022).

5. Activity Deduction

Our goal of estimating and possibly helping in improving the quality of healthcare services can greatly benefit from the analysis of positional data. There has been much research in the field on the Mobile Workforce Management (MWM) industrial process, whose general aim is to optimize the schedules of their workers and, in general, to improve the performance of their business processes. This is usually done by annotating the trajectories of the involved people, building what is known as a semantic trajectory (Parent et al., 2013, Spaccapietra et al., 2008). A semantic trajectory can be seen as a collection of segments with initial and final timestamps, the positions between these instants, and a label for the segment (e.g. $\langle 09:00, 09:10, \text{Moving}, p_1, \dots, p_n \rangle$, where p_i 's are the detected positions). In the initial research of semantic trajectories the annotation was somehow too low-level, meaning that the labels were words such as *stopped* or *moving*. However, we need a higher level of abstraction in our activity taxonomy. Knowing that a caregiver is in the same place for 10 minutes does not help much, but knowing that the caregiver is assisting a resident to take his/her daily bath does. This semantic labelling was initially done manually by the user, but it is not realistic in our context: it is not a task the residents could (or would) do in many cases, and it could interfere with the work of the caregivers. Thus, we need an automatic system to detect and semantically annotate the trajectories of residents and caregivers.

In this work we use a similar approach as in a previous research (Brisaboa et al., 2017), where the authors use not only the positional data, but other contextual information to help detecting the (semantically meaningful) activities. That work was implemented in an outdoors environment where the workers were truck drivers, so GPS information other than position (acceleration, gyroscope, etc.) could be used. Additional information such as the road network and location data (that could be customer or enterprise-owned) was also used. Being indoors, the additional GPS information is not available for us. However, there are several elements that helped us to identify and characterize an activity:

- **Type of person:** The activities that residents carry out are different from those performed by caregivers. For example, at 1:00 pm and in the dining room, a resident is probably having lunch, but a caregiver is usually assisting residents.
- **Specific data:** Specific information about residents or caregivers can help us inform of the activity taking place. For example, their degree of dependency: residents with mobility problems might be having their meal at the specified time but at their own rooms, not in the dining room. Additional information, such as the room where the resident sleeps, is also of interest. We must highlight that all activities are not needed for all residents; e.g. an autonomous resident does not need help getting to a given location, or with their personal hygiene, but a dependant resident does.

- **Location:** some locations are directly related to a specific activity or set of activities. For example, the gym is used to practice exercise and rehabilitation. However, the activity does not need to be restricted to the location, as some residents can do exercise in their rooms or outside if the weather allows it.
- **Time:** some activities are linked to a specific time frame. Nursing homes have general schedules and timetables for different activities. Activities can also be tied to a specific day of the week or even a specific date (weekends may have different schedules).
- **Duration:** The duration of an activity may help to identify it. For example, 3 minutes in the dining room during dinner time should not be labelled as *having dinner*, but if the duration is 40 minutes it might be.

Although we have based our activity deduction on the assumption that there exists a clear and detectable correlation between time and location (i.e. timestamped positioning information) and the activity taking place, we are aware this might not be true for every possible activity within a healthcare facility. However, we only focus on the basic types of activities relevant for the nursing home we are collaborating with that had a real impact on assessing the quality of health care. Those tasks were categorized in three types, two of them for individual actions (caregivers or residents) and another one for interactions between caregivers and residents. The considered activities include, among others, the following:

- For residents: personal hygiene, getting in or out of bed, having a meal, wandering.
- For caregivers: Work in common areas, rest time.
- For interactions: a caregiver is helping a resident with his/her personal hygiene, escorting a resident to some location, feeding a resident.

Figure 4 shows a simplified version of the data model used in the activity deduction, which is a special type of semantic tagging. The tagging operation is executed as a batch process on a daily basis, and it is composed of the following steps:

1. Obtain the trajectory (the list of *Positionings*) associated to each person in the last day, and generate a list of *Segments*, which are all of the same duration (in our case, 5 minutes). Observe that there may be gaps in the list of segments if no positional information is found for the person in a 5-minute period. A segment can be either static (the person is located in the same place for a period of time) or moving (the person location changes).
2. Gather additional information for each of these trajectory segments. That information includes, of course, the person and his/her type (resident or caregiver), the location(s) present in the segment and their type (room, dining room, common area, ...), the presence of other people (based on trajectory segments from other people) and other contextual information, such as the predefined meal hours of the nursing home.
3. Use a decision tree to detect the activity associated to each segment. A reduced example of such a decision tree is shown in Figure 5. It basically considers each positioning in the segment and performs a top-down traversal of the tree, guided by the conditions present in all nodes labelled as 'Decision'. This process ends with all segments having an activity type. Note that each positioning in a segment might have a different activity type. We decided that the most frequent one would be the type associated to the segment.

- Finally, group consecutive segments with the same activity type to create each *Activity*. This step verifies if there are several people with the same activity and, if necessary, creates an *Interaction* that groups them.

Figure 4: A simplified data model used by the semantic tagging process. Source: own work.

Figure 5: A (partial) example decision tree for residents. Source: own work.

Consider, for example, an autonomous resident that is alone at his/her bathroom from 8:15 to 8:25. There would be 3 segments associated to this time lapse (considering 5-minute segments). The activity would be detected as “Resident - Personal hygiene” for all segments, and they would be grouped as a single activity with the same type. Other resident, in this case a dependant one, is detected in the corridor that goes from his/her room to the dining room, from 1:00 to 1:11 pm, accompanied by a caregiver, and after that he/she stays in the dining room until 1:40, in this case alone. The trajectory would be divided into 8 segments, the first two being merged in one activity labelled as “Interaction - Escorting resident” and the remaining 6 merged into another activity,

labelled as “Having a meal”. An entry in the *Interaction* collection would be created only for the first activity. Note that, if we track the positions each minute, the third segment (from 1:10 to 1:15) would have the two activity types, but since “Having a meal” is most frequent (4 out of 5), this is the label assigned to the segment.

6. User interface

The Exploitation Module enables the final user to communicate with the system and query the diverse data stored and managed by the already explained modules. It was implemented as a client web application developed using JavaScript (vue.js) and a REST API server application developed in Java. It also includes C++ code for the communication with the *indRep* compact data structure and a small connector to access it, which was implemented using Node.js addons.

Figure 6: View of the last known position of each resident in the nursing home. Source: own work.

Our system includes the basic record manipulation characteristic of any other already implemented systems (workers, residents, medicines, shifts, etc.), but it also includes two additional features that specifically deal with the dynamic and spatio-temporal nature of the data and quality measurements:

- Representation of dynamic trajectories.
- View detailed statistics by activity or caregiver.

First, an essential view for the final users will be to locate every resident and every caregiver in their last known position in the building as it is displayed in Figure 6. This could be useful to find a resident who is missing or if, for example, he/she is having a visit and should come to the reception area.

Our proposed interface allows the final user to reproduce the indoor movements of any resident or caregiver individually. By selecting a resident and a particular date, their path throughout the day will be dynamically displayed on a map, as shown in Figure 7. The speed of the marker representing the person is proportional to the speed of his/her movements, and it can be changed at any time by the final user. This feature is adapted to a 24h format, as it is the most demanded

query by the nursing home. A time selector at the bottom of the map allows to pause the simulation at a particular time. In addition, if the marker representing the moving person is clicked, a pop-up with a list of the caregivers supporting him/her in that particular moment will appear. Due to the semantic tags given during the activity deduction phase, our system is able to aggregate and calculate the time spent by a moving person performing any activity. This is displayed as a list on the right section of the screen, below a link to the complete record of the patient in the form of a badge with the full name and an image of the resident (e.g. Alba Rodríguez spent 7 hours and 9 minutes resting in her room on July 2, 2021).

To complete the accumulative time analysis, another view, *statistics*, allows the final user to study aggregated times by activity that can be displayed as a global overview of the nursing home, or it can be filtered by resident or caregiver.

Figure 7: The user interface showing the map of the nursing home, the path traversed by a particular resident on a particular day and the amount of time spent by that resident on each activity during the day until that moment. Source: own work.

7. Evaluation and conclusions

After the system was completed, the local nursing home *Mayores* tested it to determine whether it met their expectations and improved their services. After the evaluation period, all the objectives were achieved. They emphasized the importance of the new capability of tracking residents inside the facilities and the ease of finding anomalous cases in residents routines.

The proposed work allows constant and precise monitoring of residents, which not only improves the quality of life of the elderly by offering them more personalized and timely care, but also permits the assessment of the quality of the offered services and optimizes efficiency in the management of medical resources and workers. Besides, a safer and more comfortable environment is promoted by allowing for a rapid response to any undesirable resident behaviour. This system does not bother residents in any way, while offering peace of mind to families and allowing healthcare professionals to focus on comprehensive care. Thus, from a social perspective, we believe our work has provided valuable improvements.

In conclusion, a novel system has been designed and implemented using a wide range of technologies to support the necessities of a real enterprise. The rudimentary position tracking systems were upgraded to a feasible automatic indoor positioning solution. The amount of information generated by this new strategy is dealt with compact data structures, reducing space usage without jeopardizing query times. Those compressed positions are tagged with semantic information that enables individual activity analysis. Last, a user-friendly interface lets the final user interact with the gathered and calculated information.

From a research perspective, we believe that some aspects or ideas of our system might be valuable for future research. The loosely coupled architecture that includes a module that makes the system independent of the hardware positioning system, although not completely novel, was effectively proven in a real environment. Additionally, the use of a compact data structure like *indRep* might help scale any spatio-temporal systems that is able to associate a label to each position (either indoors or outdoors).

As a note on future works, we have already begun to design new adaptors to integrate our proposed solution with different third-party systems that are popular in the nursing-homes context, such as *Gacela* (Oesía, 2024). Another direction to follow would be upgrading the system to use Bluetooth 5.1 (or higher). These recent versions of Bluetooth incorporate new improvements in terms of device localization and, specifically, the identification of the direction from which a signal comes. Finally, two of the main limitations of this work are automatic alarms and remote access querying, both features commented by the nursing home administrators. As the proposed system stores the position of the residents and the activities performed, it would be useful if it automatically alerts about atypical behaviour (e.g. a resident did not move as much as expected in the last 10 days.). On the other hand, enabling remote access through a simplified interface would allow families to view the activities and the status of their elders, improving the experience and the quality of the service.

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the viability of the compact data representation are available in <https://gitlab.lbd.org.es/lbd-open/indrep>.

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